

Welcome to the Winter 2009 issue of *DDI Directions*. Fall was a busy season for the DDI community, with a variety of activities designed to move the DDI project forward. We are truly fortunate to have such a dedicated set of individuals working to ensure that the standard is understood and used effectively. Review these pages to learn more!

Mary Vardigan, Director, DDI Alliance

DDI Training Provided

In Germany...

During the first week of November, [DDI 3.0 training](#) organized and sponsored by GESIS was held at Schloss Dagstuhl, an informatics center near Wadern, Germany, that is part of the Leibniz Association.

Participants in the course learned how to work with DDI 3.0 and brought use cases from their own institutions.

In the U.S....

On December 3, the National Opinion Research Center (NORC) sponsored [a day of training](#) in Bethesda,

Maryland, on DDI and [SDMX](#). Response to the workshop was so high that many potential participants had to be turned away. Additional training will be planned in coming months.

Group Outlines Best Practices

An [Expert Workshop on DDI best practices](#), organized and sponsored by the DDI Alliance, GESIS, the Minnesota Population Center, and the Open Data Foundation, was held November 10-14 at Dagstuhl in Germany. The objective was to develop a set of best practices papers for both technical and business cases.

The workshop generated papers on the following topics:

- Controlled vocabularies
- Governance

DDI 3.0 Training at Dagstuhl. From left, Andias Wira-Alam, GESIS; Georgios Tassoukis, IZA; Nicole Kirgis, University of Michigan

- Creating a DDI Profile
- Use of DDI 3.0 Schemes
- Versioning and Publication
- URNs and Entity Resolution
- DDI Identifiers
- Workflows
- High-Level Architectural Model
- DDI as Content for Registries

Working Groups are continuing to work on the best practice documents with the goal of publishing them on the DDI Alliance Web site in early spring.

DDI Web Site to be Redesigned

The Usability and Outreach Group (UOG) of the Alliance has begun to work on revamping the DDI site to be more effective for different user audiences.

The new site will take a data life cycle approach and will tailor content according to the type of Web site visitor. It will also be enhanced with new graphics and new content.

To contribute to the effort, please contact the [UOG](#).

Save the Dates

- May 25, 2009 ~ DDI Expert Committee Meeting, Tampere, Finland
- May 26, 2009 - DDI Workshop on 2.0 to 3.0

DDI Best Practices Workshop at Dagstuhl. From left, Ken Miller, UK Data Archive; Wolfgang Zenk-Möltgen, GESIS; Stefan Kramer, Yale University; Maarten Hoogerwerf, DANS; Rob Grim, University of Tilburg

DDI Best Practices Workshop at Dagstuhl. Clockwise from left, Jeremy Iverson, Algenta Technology; Nikos Askitas, IZA; Chuck Humphrey, University of Alberta

- Migration, [IASSIST 2009](#), Tampere, Finland; other DDI sessions to follow on May 27-29
- July 2009 ~ DDI Training in ICPSR Summer Program, Cornell University, Ithaca, NY (specific dates TBD)

- December 3, 2009 - Half-day workshop on DDI 3, sponsored by DDI Alliance, held at IZA, Bonn, Germany
- December 4, 2009 - DDI European User Group Meeting, IZA, Bonn